

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS AND WAYS TO IMPROVE BANKING FINANCIAL SERVICES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *The efficient operation of commercial banks is an important factor in ensuring high and sustainable rates of economic development, the introduction of scientific and technological progress, and the development of infrastructure. The aim of the article is to search modern role of commercial banks in the formation of an effective state economy in Uzbekistan and analyze new forms of financial services provided to clients.*

Keywords and phrases: *large-scale investment, Tax Code, relevance, effectiveness, income tax, property tax, financial resources, equipment*

In Uzbekistan, increased attention is paid to improving the activities of the country's commercial banks, active work is being carried out to introduce international standards for the functioning of commercial banks, to attract funds to Uzbekistan from foreign markets in the form of syndicated loans, to mobilize domestic financial resources and their effective placement in accordance with the programs of the state development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

At the same time, large-scale investment continues in the extractive industries, and above all, in the oil industry, as an industry through which initial stability and macroeconomic balance in the country's economy are ensured, and national security is ensured.

The legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at supporting investments in various sectors of the economy. The republic has developed a system of benefits and preferences aimed at the effective implementation of investment projects. For example, the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for investment tax preferences for corporate income tax and property tax [2].

The role and task of commercial banks in Uzbekistan is precisely to promote the most optimal investment flow of their own and attracted financial resources. In a market economy, this is achieved through the provision by commercial banks of the most diverse package of banking services, among which a special place is occupied by financial services.

To date, a sufficiently favorable macroeconomic and regulatory environment has already been created in Uzbekistan for the further development of leasing. On the part of the state, there is a complete understanding of the need for the development of leasing and support for leasing at the legislative level.

The main source of financing for leasing transactions are loans from second-tier banks, which account for 87% of the total financing of transactions. The rest of the transactions are financed by own funds [3].

It should be noted that second-tier banks have restrictions set by the National Bank in terms of financing their subsidiaries in the amount of no more than 10% of equity capital.

This requirement is a deterrent to the development of leasing, and many leasing companies, if there is a demand for equipment, are unable to finance leasing transactions.

The solution to this problem is possible by attracting foreign investment. With the growth of experience in the field of leasing, as well as the transition to IFRS, other leasing companies have the potential to enter the external borrowing market [4].

Uzbekistan has built the basis of a market economy and is now developing it more and more actively. One of the important aspects for accelerating the pace of integration into the world economic space is the creation of the most effective ways of organizing cash flows that contribute to the growth of interstate trade. The central place in the implementation of economic reforms belongs to finance and financial institutions. As we move forward towards the liberalization of the economy, the financial system adapts to new conditions, ensuring a balanced development of the national economy and its individual subjects.

The economic successes of modern Uzbekistan are largely associated with the rapid and efficient development of the banking sector. Second-tier banks in Uzbekistan have made some progress in their development. According to leading Western experts in this area, they have become one of the leading financial institutions in the CIS countries.

It should be noted that there are disputes about the essence of the concept of "financial services" in the specialized literature. In my opinion, closer to the exact definition of "financial services" should include the provision of services to ensure cash flows on a paid basis.

Among modern financial services, such as leasing, factoring and trust operations will certainly become in demand, since all of them meet the needs of consumers of financial services to the maximum extent and are in demand in the financial market [3].

All these forms of financial services can be classified as relatively new in the Uzbek financial services market. However, the world experience of their application shows their relevance and effectiveness in certain areas of rationalization of the use of financial resources.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, which needs to accelerate the pace of development and improve the living standards of the population, it is vitally necessary to develop and deepen new and already introduced financial services on a large scale.

Each of the competing domestic banks strives to satisfy the claims of customers in terms of the structure of banking financial services as much as possible. Growing competition in the sector of the economy under consideration determines the high rates of development of new instruments of financial services.

REFERENCES:

1. Mahkamov S.G. Stability of a commercial bank and rating systems for its assessment. - T.: Finance and statistics, 2009. P. 121
2. Balabanov I.T. Banks and banking. - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2009. P. 32
3. Rose. P. Banking management. - M.: Delo Ltd., 2011. P. 45
4. Edwin J. Dolan. Money, banking and monetary policy. - St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg ORCHESTRA, 1994. P. 34